

MULTIPLE FORMATION OF SPEECH TRAINING PREVENTION INSPECTORS

Scientific adviser - Akhmedova Khulkar Olimjonovna,
*Associate Professor of the Department of General Educational Disciplines,
Specialized Branch of the Tashkent state law university*

Miraliev Mirkamol Mirazizovich
*2 st year student of the Specialized branch of the
Tashkent State Law University*

Annotation The article deals with the problem of the formation of professional communicative competence in the training of future law enforcement officers, for whom communicative competence is one of the main indicators of professionalism in their future career.

Key words: communication skills, competence, professionalism, Russian language, law enforcement officer.

The need to train modern personnel who know several languages, conduct scientific work in Russian, improve the methodology of language teaching, all this is a requirement of the labor market. And also, the organization of methodological work; improving teaching methods based on an integrative approach; study of foreign experience; the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies in the teaching of a professionally oriented Russian language at law schools is one of the priority tasks.

Russian methodologists define professionally oriented education as education based on taking into account the needs of students in learning a foreign language, dictated by the peculiarities of the future profession or specialty, which, in turn, require its study.[6]

As a rule, the requirements that apply to a person's professional speech in any area of his social activity are quite high, and they are especially high if this area is inextricably linked with such concepts as legal protection and law enforcement. [4]

Stages of development of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the medium and long term and is the basis for the development of sectoral programs and a set of measures in this area. As a result, the main end result of the new educational strategy should not be a system of knowledge, skills and abilities, but a set of key competencies declared by the state in the intellectual, socio-political, communication, information and other fields.

The problem of the formation of professional communicative competence is especially clearly revealed when organizing the training of future law enforcement officers, for whom communicative competence is one of the main indicators of professionalism. Professional communication of law enforcement officers is conditioned by a wide range of socio-cultural spheres of the functioning of law and the social functions of the language of law as a tool for transmitting social control information to the addressee.

The specificity of the language of lawyers is manifested in the integration of special linguistic means of legal science and law enforcement practice (legislation), which is expressed in the fusion of scientific, official business and journalistic speech styles, in the features of their use in legal texts. On the one hand, the language of law serves communication in the administrative and legal sphere, in a purely legal professional environment, on the other hand, due to the fact that legal relations permeate the entire society and concern almost every person, written legal texts can perform the functions of communication and influence in a variety of areas and environments of communication.

The use of new forms, methods, programs and promising initiatives that contribute to the development of higher legal education is an effective implementation of the results of scientific developments in lawmaking. [1]

Thus, the actions and behavior of employees that are fair and understandable to the population are of a special nature, since they directly affect the possibility of committing an offense or crime. [2]

Modular design of the educational process involves changes in the assessment of students' achievements. The study of each module should be completed with a certain form of control, the purpose of which is to enable students and the teacher to find out how this part of the course has been mastered, evaluate what has been achieved and receive information about the problems. [5]

For cognitive activity, methodological aids and visual teaching aids, terminological dictionaries, slides, posters, tables, diagrams, electronic textbooks, which students not only view, but also comment out loud, can serve. [3]

Therefore, the formation of communicative competence in teaching the Russian language in the conditions of obtaining legal knowledge in the legal direction has its own specifics, since it is carried out in the context of professional training, taking into account the future profession.

Literature

1. Akhmedova, Kh. O. Terminological features of legal texts. Young scientist. - 2022. - No. 1 (396). — S. 266-268. <https://moluch.ru>
2. Akhmedova, Kh. and Khalikova, A. 2022. Speech culture of behavior is a significant professional duty of every crime prevention inspector. Society and innovation. 3, 2/S (April 2022), 239–245. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol3-iss2/S-pp239-245>.
3. Akhmedova, Kh. O. Terminological system as a symbolic model in the field of knowledge Young scientist. - 2022. - No. 1 (396). — S. 264-266. <https://moluch.ru>
4. Khalikova, A., Umbetaliyev, A. & Akhmedova, H. 2022. The culture of speech is a fundamental priority in the activities of prevention inspectors. Society and innovation. 3, 4/S (May 2022), 84–90. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol3-iss4/S-pp84-90>.

5. Chernilevsky D.V. Didactic technologies in higher education: Textbook. M.: UNITI, 2002. 436 p.

6. H. Ahmedova, D. Hoshimova, N. Niyozova. "On the basis of an integrated course, teaching professionally oriented foreign language vocabulary to students of non-linguistic specialties." ASEAN Journal on Science & Technology for Development Vol 39, No. 4, 2022, 237241 <https://zenodo.org/record/7030819> © The Author(s) 2022. This article is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International license. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7030819

7. Lola Yunusovna Akramova, Khulkar Olimzhonovna Akhmedova, Feruza Khashimova. (2020). THE PROBLEMS OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE PANDEMIC. PalArch's Journal of Archeology of Egypt / Egyptology, 17(7), 8577-8583. Retrieved from <https://archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/3642>

8. Sidorova N.I. Abstract "The role of the Russian language in the structure of professional competence of an employee of the Federal Penitentiary Service of Russia" UDC 343.8 LBC 67.409.022 C34